

PROMOTION OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG THE POPULATION

G.A. Turaxodjayeva

Director of the Andijan branch of the Republican Center for Training
and Specialization of Secondary Medical and Pharmaceutical Workers

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the population is informed about maintaining a healthy lifestyle, eating healthy and living a long life, the work being done in Uzbekistan in this regard, and the work that is equally important for young people to grow up healthy. given comments are made.

Valeology is the science of health. In the ancient Roman language, Valeo means healthy, that is, be healthy. Valeology is a science that studies the individual health of a person, the mechanisms and methods of its maintenance.

Forming a healthy lifestyle.

A healthy lifestyle includes productive work, active recreation, physical education and sports, physical education, personal hygiene, proper nutrition, giving up harmful habits, mental and spiritual nutrition, regular medical examinations. includes concepts such as

Step-by-step development of strengthening one's health;

Maintaining a perfect physical condition of one's body;

Take steps every day to be mentally fit for good health. The first and most powerful factor in the formation of a lifestyle is the family. Family environment, family routines are the way of life of the family.

It is important to create a healthy lifestyle among the population, mass equip all layers of the population with hygienic knowledge, and teach them to acquire hygienic skills.

A number of cultural and educational activities are of particular importance in protecting the health of the population, improving the quality of medical services, promoting a healthy lifestyle among young people, and improving medical culture. It is nutrition that ensures a person's vital activity, normal growth and development, strengthens his health and helps prevent diseases.

It should not be forgotten that human health is the main basis for his happy and prosperous life.

After achieving national independence with the honor of independence, our republic was recognized by the world as an equal member of the world community.

It is the demand of the time for the medical system of our republic to find its place in

the conditions of the market economy, to provide high-quality emergency medical care to the population, and to work on the basis of pure humanitarian policy. . After the independence of our republic, important and effective changes were made in the health care system. Maintaining and protecting the health of the population of our republic is one of the main tasks of our independent state.

In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", "National Program of Personnel Training", "State Program for Reforming the Health Care System", "Citizens' Health Care", strengthening the provision of medical care to the population by nurses with all measures, care for the protection of motherhood and childhood, the development of a healthy generation, and the efforts towards the development of our national medicine and pharmaceuticals accelerate the efforts. Therefore, a nurse should constantly work on herself, improve her knowledge, step by step, provide medical care to the patient, and give her spiritual support. Because the nurse communicates with the patient more than the doctor.

Training of world-class medical personnel is the need of the hour. Based on this demand, highly qualified nurses who work perfectly with new medical techniques, who can evaluate the patient's condition, make a diagnosis based on the symptoms of the disease, and make an independent plan for the patient's problem are very necessary. At the same time, the nurse should embody politeness, openness, politeness, good manners, attentiveness to patients, orderliness, mediocrity, neatness, modesty and other features during communication with patients in the course

of daily activities. Such a situation is very necessary for every person, especially for a medical worker - a nurse. A nurse who takes these into account will not have difficulties in life and work, and will be respected by patients and the community. The history of medicine occupies a special place among medical knowledge. It provides a generalizing unique understanding of the historical development of medicine and its past up to the present day, reveals the laws of development of medicine and, accordingly, determines its future directions. The history of medicine is an important and fundamental part of the history of humanity.

Concept of health.

In all developed countries, health is considered the most important wealth of a person. A healthy person has great power in any society, performs a creative function, is considered a source of human joy, intellectual and physical abilities.

Valeology is aimed at forming a conscious stable and positive attitude of students to theoretical, practical and independent training of physical education, improves health, increases the productivity of educational processes, and forms elements of physical culture.

Health is very important in human life, especially in youth. The level of health causes a person's professional maturity and creative growth.

According to experts, 20% of population health is due to genetic factors; 20-30% depends on environmental influences, 40-50% on lifestyle and 10% on health care activities. Lifestyle is an important factor in health.

Analyzing the situation in the field of youth health, it is possible to understand that this problem needs to be solved immediately. It is impossible to solve the issues of spiritual, moral and physical development without making fundamental changes in the field of improving the health of the growing generation. Therefore, the concept of health of the generation should be aimed at forming the desire of young people to radically change their attitude to their health and organizing healthy recreation.

At the moment, the scientific pedagogical concept developed in the field of valeology is designed to solve specific issues regarding the health of young people, healthy physical education that satisfies the personal needs of a person, and the forms and methods of a healthy lifestyle. Healthy lifestyle and health.

According to experts, 40-50% of the population's health depends on lifestyle, harmful habits, improper diet, excessive consumption of alcohol and tobacco, too much sitting (stress), pollution of the environment leads to various diseases

(cardiovascular and respiratory system diseases, stomach - it is known to cause intestinal function disorders x.k). Abu Ali Ibn Sina attached great importance to health care. Alloma has repeatedly noted the importance of regular exercise in preventing diseases. Physical education and health

Physical education is a part of general culture in the society and it is one of the spheres of social activity aimed at developing physical abilities of a person and strengthening his health.

It is possible to talk about the state of physical culture in society through the following indicators: the level of people's health and physical culture. Level of use of physical education in production and life of education and training spheres: use of free time, system of physical education, character, development of mass sports, achievements in sports. Basic elements of physical education. We can give an example of physical exercises, complexes and competitions on them, body training, cocktail and life hygiene, tourism.

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